

Based on the Train-the-Trainer concept on DMPs and RDMO. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15771036](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15771036)

How to Plan and Run a Workshop on Data Management Plans (DMPs)

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Purpose

This guide provides trainers conducting DMP workshops with a step-by-step approach to planning and running an effective session, ensuring participants leave with a solid understanding of DMP fundamentals. It also includes a teaching script example, with learning objectives and a suggested duration.

Organising a workshop to introduce Data Management Plans (DMPs) is a valuable way to support researchers, librarians, and community members in harmonising the handling of research data. This guide provides a step-by-step approach to planning and running an effective workshop, ensuring participants leave with a solid understanding of DMPs, their benefits, and how they are created.

This guide is based on the “**DMP – Level 1: Fundamentals**” module from the *Train-the-Trainer Concept on DMPs and RDMO* (TTT Concept) [1]. The target group for this level are researchers and community members who are new to DMPs and seek a structured entry point into research data management (RDM) practices. RDM professionals and National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) consortium members conducting DMP workshops can use this level as a **starting point to provide training and support** within their communities, helping participants gain confidence in creating and working with DMPs. The practical guide *23 Training Things For Effective Webinars* [2] was also used as a reference.

The guide was developed during the incubator project with the Chemistry Consortium of the NFDI ([NFDI4Chem](https://www.nfdi4chem.org/)) during the integration phase of the NFDI basic service on data management plans ([DMP4NFDI](https://www.nfdi4chem.org/dmp4nfdi/)).

Step 1. Define the Target Group & Workshop Goals

Begin by clearly defining both the objectives of your workshop and the target audience, as one will often shape the other. Reflect on what you want participants to achieve by the end while also considering their prior knowledge, disciplinary background, and specific needs. For example, you can demonstrate ways to integrate DMPs into everyday workflows or address real concerns with practical solutions from your discipline.

The TTT Concept outlines the following learning objectives for a workshop on DMP fundamentals (Level 1), suitable for those with little or no prior experience of using DMP:

Participants will be able to...

- A. Name and explain the general components of a DMP.
- B. Explain and discuss the relevance and benefits of DMPs in research projects.
- C. Identify relevant funding institutions and their DMP requirements.
- D. Write a simple DMP with guidance.
- E. Recognise the concept and relevance of machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs).

Step 2. Plan the Workshop Structure

Design a detailed agenda that balances informative sessions with interactive activities and documents logistics (e.g. materials to be used, links to be shared). If your audience comprises participants with different levels of expertise on DMPs, consider providing two or three versions of the same exercise for different levels.

At the end of this guide, you will find a [teaching script example](#) for a workshop on DMP fundamentals that you can reuse and adapt to reflect discipline-specific information. The teaching script incorporates a live demo of the [Research Data Management Organiser \(RDMO\)](#), a DMP tool that supports research projects in planning, implementing and administering all research data management tasks.

Step 3. Prepare Materials and Setup

Ensure that you have all necessary support and materials ready before the workshop:

- **Responsibilities & Roles:** Define the roles and tasks of each presenter and moderator, making everyone aware of learning objectives and timeline. Tasks

include, but are not limited to, screen sharing, chat moderation (e.g. keeping an eye out for questions and sharing links) and timekeeping.

- **Presentation Slides:**
 - Create clear and engaging slides using simple language and visualisations.
 - Provide written instructions and the duration of all activities.
 - Use storytelling methods and try to incorporate as many analogies and real-world examples as possible that are directly related to the day-to-day work of your community. For example, start with horror stories (e.g. without DMPs), then move on to lessons learned, and finally end with related DMP content explanation.
- **Handouts & Materials:** Prepare and test in advance the (interactive) materials you would use during the workshop to engage your audience (e.g. polls, quizzes, summary sheets)¹. Avoid using too many different tools (e.g. Mentimeter, Miro, EthePad) as this can be confusing.
- **Digital Tools:** Familiarise yourself with the software and online platforms that will be used during the workshop. If you are delivering an **RDMO live demo**, we recommend introducing a relatable scenario on a slide first, explaining to participants who the RDMO user is (e.g. a researcher) and the steps they would take in the software. After the live demonstration, summarise again the steps taken and what goal was achieved.
- **Feedback Survey:** Allocate the final 10–15 minutes of the workshop to gather participants' feedback². This is the best way to identify areas for improvement and understand what participants took away from the workshop.

Step 4. Facilitation Tips

Effective facilitation can greatly enhance the learning experience. Keep these tips in mind:

- **Meet in advance for a technical check:** 30 min before starting to test slides, audio, connection, other apps, etc.
- **Know your first 5 minutes & stay calm:** Have a script for your first minutes to have a great start. This will boost your own confidence, as well as participants' confidence in you and the workshop.
- **Engage participants:**
 - Use [icebreakers](#) to activate the audience.

¹ The extended version of the one-pager "23 training things for effective webinars" includes suggestions for incorporating interactive materials: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14792536>

² The "Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management" provides ideas for gathering feedback and a template for a post-workshop evaluation form (Units 13 & 22): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5773203>

- Encourage questions and discussions to create an interactive environment. Remember to allow 20-second pauses for participants to ask or answer questions.
- **Be inclusive:** Make sure that all voices are heard. Be aware of your audience's potential accessibility needs and adapt your approach accordingly, offering different types of formats and contributions (e.g. small group discussions and individual contributions, which can be made verbally or in writing).
- **Stay flexible:** Be prepared to adjust your plan based on time constraints or participant needs.
- **Use clear language:** Avoid jargon, and explain technical terms to ensure understanding.
- **Be patient:** you may have to answer the same questions or explain the same terms multiple times, and that's OK.

Step 5. Follow-Up and Community Building

After the workshop, maintain momentum by fostering a community of practice:

- **Workshop materials:** Share workshop slides, templates, and resource links.
- **Post-workshop feedback:**
 - After the workshop, take time to exchange feedback with your co-trainers to share impressions, reflect on challenges, and refine both your teaching approach and the workshop programme.
 - To understand the long-term impact, consider sending a short follow-up survey after approximately six months to learn whether and how participants are using DMPs in their daily work and support activities.
- **Regular updates:** Share follow-up materials, such as articles or webinars, to keep participants engaged. You could also offer consultation hours for participants working on their DMPs.

Step 6. Suggested Resources

Provide participants with resources to continue their learning journey, e.g.,

- Funder or discipline-specific [DMP templates or guidelines](#)
- [RDMO Documentation](#)
- Basic readings on [maDMPs](#)

Teaching script example

The following teaching script is based on introductory workshop materials on Data Management Plans (DMPs) developed by Vandendorpe et al. [3], as well as introductory RDMO workshop materials developed by Gonzalez-Ocanto et al. [4]. It is designed for an online workshop format and intended for a suggested duration of 3–4 hours, which can be delivered as a single session or split into two shorter sessions. The target group are those with little or no prior experience of using DMPs. At the end of the workshop, participants should be able to:

- A.** Name and explain the general components of a DMP;
- B.** Explain and discuss the relevance and benefits of DMPs in research projects;
- C.** Identify relevant funding institutions and their DMP requirements;
- D.** Write a simple DMP with guided support;
- E.** Recognise the concept and relevance of machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs).

To encourage interaction and active participation, collaborative tools such as virtual whiteboards or polling platforms (e.g., Miro or Mentimeter) could be used. Collaborative editors (e.g., HedgeDoc or Etherpad) are also an alternative for note-taking, group work, or shared reflections throughout the workshop.

Teaching script example

Learning Objectives:

- A. Name and explain the general components of a DMP.
- B. Explain and discuss the relevance and benefits of DMPs in research projects.
- C. Identify relevant funding institutions and their DMP requirements.
- D. Write a simple DMP with guided support.
- E. Recognise the concept and relevance of machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs).

WL: Workshop Leader | **P:** Participants

Unit	(Working Method) Content	Step	Learning objective	Material	Duration (Estimated)
1	Welcome & Orientation		N/A		Total: 15-25 min
1.1	(Chatstorm ³ / Talk) Icebreaker	WL & P introductions		chat function / interactive tool	~5-10 min
1.2	(Ideas Out Loud) Expectations	P speak		chat function / interactive tool	~5-10 min
1.3	(Talk) Agenda	WL speaks		Slides	~3-5 min
2	Introduction to DMPs		A		Total: 5 min

³ Chatstorm: Each participant individually answers a brief open question via chat, e.g.: "Where did you last go on holiday?"

Unit	(Working Method) Content	Step	Learning objective	Material	Duration (Estimated)
2.1	(Poll) Have you ever created a DMP?	P act		Interactive poll tool	~3 min
2.2	(Talk) What is a DMP?	WL speaks		Slides	~2 min
3	Anatomy of a DMP		A		Total: 20 min
3.1	(Talk) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chapter 1: Administrative project-specific information • Chapter 2: Roles, responsibilities and obligations • Chapter 3: Budget, costs and resources • Chapter 4: Description of the data to be collected and shared • Chapter 5: Data documentation • Chapter 6: Data access and publishing • Chapter 7: Further points 	WL speaks		Slides	~10 min
3.2	(Exercise) Assign questions to DMP chapters	P act		Slides or interactive tool	~10 min
4	Examples and Templates		A		Total: 10-12 min
4.1	(Talk)	WL speaks		Slides	~6-8 min

Unit	(Working Method) Content	Step	Learning objective	Material	Duration (Estimated)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General templates • Discipline-specific templates • Discipline-specific examples • Other DMP examples 				
4.2	Q&A	P speak			~3-5 min
5	Difference between DMPs and other types of documents		A		Total: 15-20 min
5.1	(Talk) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DMP vs. research guidelines • DMP vs. research data policy • Living vs. static documents • Section vs. entirety of the proposal 	WL speaks		Slides	~8-10 min
5.2	(Exercise) Truth or lie	P act		Slides or interactive tool	~5 min
5.3	Q&A	P speak			~3-5 min
6	Importance and benefits		B		Total: 10-15 min
6.1	(Exercise) Horror story	P act		Slides	~5 min

Unit	(Working Method) Content	Step	Learning objective	Material	Duration (Estimated)
6.2	(Talk) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DMP role in the research data life cycle • DMP benefits 	WL speaks		Slides	~5-8 min
6.3	Q&A	P speak			~3-5 min
7	Writing a DMP		C; D		Total: 25-30 min
7.1	(Talk) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders and Timing • Funder requirements and templates • Length and details 	WL speaks		Slides	~3-6 min
7.2	(Exercise) Write a DMP	P act		Slides	~15 min
7.3	(Talk) DMP Quality Check	WL speaks		Slides	~1-2 min
7.4	Q&A	P speak			~3-5 min
8	DMP Tool: RDMO		D		Total: 20-25 min
8.1	(Talk) What is RDMO?	WL speaks		Slides	~3-5 min
8.2	(Live Demo) DMP creation in RDMO	WL speaks		Slides, RDMO	~15 min

Unit	(Working Method) Content	Step	Learning objective	Material	Duration (Estimated)
8.3	Q&A	P speak			~3-5 min
9	Machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs)		E		Total: 10-15 min
9.1	(Talk) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition • Stakeholder interactions • Essential components of the maDMP vision • Benefits and importance for researchers 	WL speaks		Slides	~4-8 min
9.2	(Exercise) Truth or Lie	P act		Slides or interactive tool	~5 min
9.3	Q&A	P speak			~3-5 min
10	Wrap-Up & Feedback		N/A		Total: 15 min
10.1	(Ideas out loud) Reflection & Recap: What do you take away?	P speak			~5min
10.2	(Evaluation form/ Questionnaire) Feedback	P act			~10min

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References

- [1] Gonzalez Ocanto, M., Diederichs, K., Schönau, S., Wallace, D., & Windeck, J. (2025). DMP4NFDI Train-the-Trainer Concept on Data Management Plans and RDMO. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15771036>
- [2] Hausen, D. A., Jordan, S., Manske, A., & Schröter, A. (2025). 23 TrainingThings For Effective Webinars (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14792536>
- [3] Vandendorpe, J., Lindstaedt, B., Diederichs, K., Fuerst, J., Sauerwein, T., Di Giorgio, S., & Gonzalez Ocanto, M. (2026, March 17). Awareness in Data Management and Analysis for Industry and Research. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19069488>
- [4] Gonzalez Ocanto, M., Schönau, S., Wallace, D., & Windeck, J. (2025). Workshop RDMO for Editors—13. & 14. November 2025. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17780963>